

MulitaMiner: Transforming Heterogeneous Technical Reports into Structured Data Using LLMs

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Abstract. *This paper presents MulitaMiner, a tool based on large language models designed to extract and transform vulnerability information from heterogeneous reports into structured data. The evaluation compares results against structured baselines using semantic similarity metrics such as ROUGE-L and BERTScore. For empirical validation, a dataset was constructed containing 6,700 vulnerabilities extracted from 129 OpenVAS reports on DockerHub containers, enabling a systematic, reproducible, and quantitative assessment of the tool's performance.*

1. Introduction

The volume of software vulnerabilities continues to grow, with over 30,000 annual records recently registered in the *National Vulnerability Database* (NVD) [NIST 2025]. Additionally, critical vulnerabilities often present remediation times exceeding 30 days [Edgescan 2025], widening the window of exposure to attacks. This scenario is further compounded by the fact that much of the relevant information is available in unstructured formats, such as *Portable Document Format* (PDF) reports, security bulletins from *Computer Security Incident Response Teams* (CSIRTs) within the national ecosystem of the Brazilian National Research and Education Network (RNP), vendor notes, and advisories, which detail vulnerability descriptions, affected systems, attack vectors, and mitigation recommendations. This dispersion hinders automated knowledge extraction and limits large-scale analysis.

In this context, vulnerability management becomes essential for securing distributed network and system infrastructures, including servers and services, and relies heavily on reports generated by automated scanning tools [Foreman 2019, Security 2024], a process that can be challenging due to the diversity and inconsistency of such data. The heterogeneity of these reports, combined with inconsistencies in vulnerability repositories, hampers automated analysis and structured data integration, and compromises the quality of analytical models [Dabholkar 2023, Mitchell et al. 2025, Croft et al. 2023, Guo et al. 2024]. As a result, manual processes and *ad hoc* solutions remain widely employed [Rafati 2025]. Although recent approaches based on *Large Language Models* (LLMs) have advanced structured extraction of security data, they still lack more focused empirical evaluations and reproducible pipelines that demonstrate their applicability in real-world distributed network and system scenarios [Hu et al. 2024, Ferrag et al. 2025].

As shown in Table 1, recent works have advanced the structured extraction of unstructured documents through LLMs and hybrid strategies, yet still present limita-

tions in cybersecurity scenarios and large-scale environments. In general, these solutions focus on analyzing isolated documents or specific domains, such as invoices, tables, or clinical records [Wang et al. 2024, Zhang et al. 2024, García et al. 2024], or prioritize interaction and contextual retrieval without support for structured continuous-processing pipelines [Lin 2024, Ghane et al. 2024]. Consequently, they lack essential mechanisms such as progressive segmentation, incremental consolidation, deduplication, and output standardization, which complicates consistent processing of large volumes of heterogeneous documents. Within the cybersecurity domain, many solutions assume pre-structured data or focus on classification and detection tasks [Gao et al. 2022, Park and Lee 2022, Sharmila 2026], failing to directly address semantic extraction from complex technical reports, such as PDFs generated by vulnerability scanners. Thus, a gap persists in building reproducible and scalable pipelines capable of consistently and integrally transforming large collections of heterogeneous reports into operational structured data. Even proposals within the cybersecurity context, such as [Machado et al. 2025], rely on fixed-size segmentation and do not incorporate adaptive chunking, configurable semantic deduplication, or systematic comparative evaluation, which can lead to context loss and the generation of redundant or inconsistent information.

Table 1. Structured extraction of unstructured documents with LLMs

Domain	Reference	Input Model	Main Approach	Models Used	Structured Representation
Business & Professional Operations	[Wang et al. 2024]	Business documents with complex layout (forms, invoices, reports)	Visual and textual layout-aware attention	LLaMA 2 / Falcon	JSON
	[Zhang et al. 2024]	Tabular content embedded in documents (tables in PDFs/spreadsheets)	Tabular data-specific reasoning	LLaMA 3.1 8B	CSV / DOCX / XLSX
	[Ghane et al. 2024]	Heterogeneous corporate documents (text + tables)	Context retrieval with document integration and response generation	Mistral 7B	JSON, XLSX
Education & Technical Knowledge	[Wang et al. 2024]	Business documents with rich layout (invoices, contracts, forms)	Traditional language models are trained to predict the next word	LLaMa 2 (7B) / Falcon (1B)	JSON
	[Lin 2024]	Technical documents and unstructured manuals (PDF)	Generation with relevant context retrieval from documents (RAG)	GPT-3.5 Turbo	JSON / Markdown
Health Sciences	[García et al. 2024]	Unstructured clinical reports and medical records	Zero-shot extraction of clinical text to JSON	GPT-3.5 / LLaMA 2	JSON
Cybersecurity	[Sharmila 2026]	Technical design documents and product specifications (PDF)	LLM-assisted threat modeling with CVE identification via RAG	LLaMa 2 / KeyBERT	JSONL
	[Gao et al. 2022]	Threat intelligence reports (unstructured text)	Entity and relation extraction for Knowledge Graph construction	NLP + DL models (BERT-based)	Knowledge Graph
	[Park and Lee 2022]	Unstructured technical security reports	Entity and relation identification	Supervised models	JSON
	[Machado et al. 2025]	Technical vulnerability reports	Modular pipeline with field identification and mapping to a unified schema	GPT-4/4.1, DeepSeek	JSON, CSV
	MulitaMiner (this work)	Unstructured technical vulnerability reports (PDF)	Intelligent segmentation and LLM-based modeling for scalable structuring	GPT-4/5, DeepSeek, LLaMA 3/4	JSON, XLSX, CSV

In this work, we propose MulitaMiner, a tool that processes heterogeneous PDF reports from vulnerability scanners, such as the *Open Vulnerability Assessment Scanner* (OpenVAS), through a pipeline that integrates scanner-oriented segmentation, token-controlled chunking, specialized prompts, multi-LLM support, semantic deduplication, and evaluation with metrics such as *BERT-based Evaluation Score* (BERTScore) and *Recall-Oriented Understudy for Gisting Evaluation, Longest Common Subsequence* (ROUGE-L), enabling scalable and reproducible data structuring. The approach was implemented in a tool supporting models such as DeepSeek, GPT-4/5, and LLaMA 3/4, resulting in the construction of a vulnerability dataset extracted from real OpenVAS reports, made publicly available to the SecDevOps community for comparative analysis. To ensure reproducibility, the source code, documentation, evaluation artifacts, and dataset

are publicly available in a GitHub repository¹.

2. Architecture

The MulitaMiner architecture was designed addressing specific challenges in the cybersecurity domain, particularly the heterogeneity, structural inconsistency, and high semantic variability of vulnerability reports generated by different scanners. Existing solutions frequently assume pre-structured inputs or rely on fixed segmentation and inflexible pipelines, which compromises context preservation, hinders consolidation of large data volumes, and introduces redundancies and inconsistencies in the results.

As illustrated in Figure 1, MulitaMiner organizes its processing into five layers (**input/extraction, preprocessing, LLMs, output, and analysis**), structured to ensure modularity, low coupling, and reproducibility. This organization explicitly addresses common limitations in existing approaches, such as the absence of adaptive semantic segmentation, ineffective deduplication, and lack of systematic evaluation mechanisms.

Figure 1. MulitaMiner data flow

Input and extraction layer: handles the ingestion of PDF reports from different scanners (e.g., OpenVAS, *Tenable Web Application Scanning* (Tenable WAS)), preserving relevant semantic structures such as titles, identifiers, and technical sections. Unlike simplified approaches based on linear text extraction, this layer incorporates Unicode normalization, encoding handling, and structural validation, reducing noise introduced by formatting artifacts typical of these reports.

Preprocessing layer: directly addresses a recurring limitation in existing solutions that use fixed-size segmentation and disregard the semantic organization of reports. MulitaMiner implements adaptive, scanner-oriented segmentation combined with token-

¹<https://github.com/AnonShield/MulitaMiner>

controlled chunking, reducing context loss and improving extraction quality. Parameterizable templates allow rapid adaptation to new report formats, while the generation of specialized prompts directs models toward consistent extraction of vulnerability attributes.

Language Models (LLMs) layer: prompts are processed by multiple models (e.g., GPT-4, GPT-5, LLaMA, and DeepSeek), enabling multi-LLM execution. Unlike monolithic pipelines, this layer enables comparative analysis between models under different configurations. Outputs are standardized through a validated JSON schema, with fallback mechanisms to handle inconsistencies, reducing structural variations commonly observed in LLM-based applications.

Output layer: consolidates results into structured formats including *JavaScript Object Notation* (JSON), *Comma-Separated Values* (CSV), *Excel Spreadsheet (Office Open XML)* (XLSX), and *Tab-Separated Values* (TSV), with automatic schema validation. To mitigate redundancies, a recurring problem in vulnerability extraction, configurable deduplication strategies are applied based on vulnerability name, textual similarity, and identifiers. This mechanism allows balancing duplicate elimination while preserving legitimate occurrences, contributing to structured data quality.

Analysis layer: integrates an optional quantitative evaluation module, absent in most solutions for this domain. Metrics such as ROUGE-L and BERTScore are used to measure structural and semantic similarity against expert-defined baselines. This enables not only validating extraction quality, but also systematically comparing different models and processing strategies, turning the tool into a controlled experimental environment.

Taken together, the proposed architecture establishes a pipeline capable of handling heterogeneous vulnerability reports in real-world cybersecurity scenarios, aiming to overcome, to the extent possible, the limitations of existing approaches by integrating adaptive segmentation, multi-LLM execution, configurable deduplication, and quantitative evaluation in a unified and reproducible workflow.

2.1. Implementation and Usage

MulitaMiner was developed in *Python* (v3.10) to process unstructured PDF documents and extract vulnerabilities through language models (LLMs). Libraries such as `langchain` (v0.2.0), `pdfplumber` (v0.11.0), `tiktoken` (v0.6.0), `pandas` (v2.1.0), `rapidfuzz` (v3.5.0), `torch` (v2.1.0), `bert-score` (v0.3.13), and `transformers` (v4.35.0), among others, were used to ensure flexibility and efficiency in natural language processing. The source code is available on GitHub¹, which also contains detailed documentation, execution examples, and the tool's parameterization options.

Execution environment: for use with cloud-based LLMs, a computer with a quad-core processor, 8 GB of RAM, and a stable internet connection (Windows, Linux, or macOS) is recommended, running Python 3.8 or higher (preferably 3.10+).

Operational requirements and limitations: use of LLM *Application Programming Interface* (API) requires valid credentials and configuration of keys in the configuration files (`src/configs/llms`) via `.env` file, and is subject to provider quota limits. The system includes retry and fallback mechanisms; however, prolonged connectivity failures may impact performance. For confidential documents, the use of local models or adherence to provider data retention policies is recommended.

3. Results

This section evaluates the extraction accuracy and consistency against the ground truth and the quality of the generated dataset, considering (i) extraction quality and (ii) its potential for future applications. The evaluation uses BERTScore and ROUGE-L, classified as Highly Similar (≥ 0.7), Moderately Similar (0.6–0.7), Low Similarity (0.4–0.6), Divergent (< 0.4), along with the Absent and Non-existent categories. Although these metrics do not capture per-entity precision, they estimate the semantic proximity between the extractions and the ground truth.

3.1. Baseline Validation

Model selection is based on the empirical evaluation of five LLMs (GPT-4, GPT-5, LLaMA 3, LLaMA 4, and DeepSeek) against three manual baselines (*ground truth*): Artifactory 5.11.0, Juice Shop, and bBWA, aiming to identify the best-performing model for vulnerability extraction in the construction of a reliable large-scale dataset. The baselines, comprising 217 vulnerabilities categorized by severity, were prepared by two specialists, with divergence validation prior to consolidation. The results guide the model selection and indirectly indicate the quality of the generated dataset.

Table 2. Vulnerabilities by severity across the 3 baselines (Ground Truths)

Severity	Artifactory 5.11.0	Juice Shop	bBWA
CRITICAL	9	0	0
HIGH	62	2	19
MEDIUM	31	3	36
LOW	3	0	3
LOG	20	29	0
Total	125	34	58

The detailed performance metric results per model and per baseline are presented in Figures 2 and 3. The evaluation considers two complementary dimensions: (i) global semantic similarity, measured by BERTScore, and (ii) structural textual proximity, estimated by the ROUGE-L metric, allowing comparison of model behavior across different vulnerability scenarios.

Overall, DeepSeek demonstrated highly competitive performance on both metrics. In terms of BERTScore (Figure 2), the model achieved high and consistent values across all scenarios, with notable results for the Juice Shop and bBWA baselines, indicating good semantic preservation of the extracted descriptions and a higher concentration of cases classified as “High Similarity”. Similarly, the ROUGE-L results (Figure 3) ranked among the highest observed, particularly for those same baselines, evidencing strong textual fidelity and structural reconstruction capacity of relevant information. This performance stems from the model’s ability to capture semantic similarity and preserve the structure of information, resulting in closer alignment with the ground truth.

Alongside extraction quality, the cost of using LLM APIs for processing the three baselines was assessed, measured by input and output token consumption. Each baseline was processed ten times, and the financial cost was estimated based on the respective providers’ pricing (in US dollars). Table 3 summarizes these results, indicating that DeepSeek presents the best balance between extraction quality, metric performance

Figure 2. BERTScore similarity results for the baselines.

(BERTScore and ROUGE-L), and processing cost, possibly owing to its ability to process data efficiently, reducing redundancies and maintaining compact representations without compromising the fidelity of extracted information.

Figure 3. ROUGE-L similarity results for the baselines.

3.2. Dataset Construction and Analysis

The dataset contains 6,700 vulnerabilities extracted from 129 PDF reports generated by the OpenVAS scanner. Each report (PDF²) corresponds to a scan of a Docker container hosted on DockerHub. The container selection and identification process is detailed in the tool's GitHub repository¹.

²Although OpenVAS supports export in CSV and other structured formats, PDFs were used because they reflect common practice among CSIRTs in the RNP ecosystem. The tool aims to support these CSIRTs in processing historical PDF reports, enabling the construction of datasets and analysis of IT infrastructure security posture based on identified vulnerabilities.

Table 3. Token consumption and estimated cost per LLM

LLM	Input Tokens	Out Tokens	Total Tokens	Cost (US\$)
DeepSeek	7,696,630	1,422,522	9,119,152	2.75
GPT-4	7,696,630	1,194,135	8,890,765	3.74
GPT-5	7,696,630	1,280,084	8,976,714	4.48
LLaMa 3	7,696,630	1,422,519	9,119,149	5.66
LLaMa 4	7,696,630	1,345,762	9,042,392	1.30
Total	38,483,150	6,665,022	45,148,172	17.95

Each report was processed individually, preserving the context of each scan and avoiding the mixing of information, which facilitates validation and comparison between models. Extracted vulnerabilities were consolidated into a structured format based on a scanner-independent schema, enabling aggregated and interoperable analyses.

Table 4. Vulnerability distribution by severity

Severity	Count	% of Total
Critical	964	14.39%
High	1,465	21.87%
Medium	1,908	28.48%
Low	494	7.37%
Log	1,869	27.90%
Total	6,700	100%

The severity distribution in the dataset spans from low-impact vulnerabilities (*Log* and *Low*) to highly critical flaws (*High* and *Critical*), in accordance with the classifications widely adopted by vulnerability scanners such as OpenVAS and by the *Common Vulnerability Scoring System* (CVSS). This diversity of severity levels indicates that the dataset encompasses different technical risk profiles, making it more representative of real-world production scenarios.

Dataset Coverage Evaluation

To estimate coverage, the dataset was compared against 6,343 vulnerabilities exported in CSV from OpenVAS, using fuzzy matching on vulnerability names and host/IP (threshold of 85%), with this CSV adopted as the baseline since it reflects the same source as the PDFs. BERTScore and ROUGE-L metrics were not applied at this stage due to incompatibility between the OpenVAS proprietary schema and the MulitaMiner structure, which would require extensive manual mapping.

The difference of 357 vulnerabilities between the total extracted (6,700) and the baseline (6,343) stems from the use of LLMs, resulting in 599 false positives and 242 false negatives. Nevertheless, results indicate satisfactory performance, with a recall of 96.18%, precision of 91.06%, and an F1-score of 0.9355, demonstrating the reliability of the approach. Additionally, reference vulnerabilities from intentionally vulnerable applications, such as OWASP Juice Shop, were used, with results summarized in Table 5.

Table 5. Estimated extraction accuracy of the dataset

Long metrics	Value	Short metrics	Value
Total in baseline (OpenVAS CSV)	6,343	Recall	0.9618 (96.18%)
Total extracted by pipeline	6,700	Precision	0.9106 (91.06%)
Unmatched (false positives)	599 (8.94%)	F1-score	0.9355
Not extracted (false negatives): 242 (3.82%)			

4. Availability and Demonstration Plan

To support validation and reuse, *MulitaMiner*'s source code is publicly available on GitHub¹, with a README containing installation instructions via virtual environment and automatic dependency management (`requirements.txt`). The fully configurable extraction pipeline is executed via a single CLI command, enabling automatic PDF processing, vulnerability extraction, and quality evaluation without manual intervention, including BERTScore examples.

For the SBRC Tools Session, the demonstration will be conducted on a standard laptop (4 vCPUs, 8GB RAM) running Windows 10+ or Ubuntu 20.04, requiring no specialized hardware, only connectivity to LLM APIs (OpenAI, Groq, DeepSeek). The demo includes comparison across multiple LLMs (GPT-4, LLaMA 3, DeepSeek), token usage and cost analysis, and real-time quality evaluation with BERTScore and ROUGE-L against structured baselines.

5. Conclusion and Future Work

This work presented *MulitaMiner*, a reproducible and scalable LLM-driven pipeline for transforming heterogeneous vulnerability reports into structured security data. By integrating adaptive scanner-aware segmentation, multi-LLM execution, semantic deduplication, and quantitative evaluation, the proposed approach advances large-scale vulnerability knowledge extraction from unstructured technical PDFs and establishes a unified framework for vulnerability intelligence engineering.

The empirical results demonstrate both scientific and operational relevance. Among the evaluated models, *DeepSeek* achieved the best quality-to-cost trade-off, consistently delivering strong performance in both BERTScore and ROUGE-L. At scale, the generated dataset, comprising 6,700 vulnerabilities extracted from 129 real OpenVAS reports, achieved 96.18% recall, 91.06% precision, and an F1-score of 93.55%, demonstrating the robustness, reproducibility, and practical viability of the proposed pipeline for SecDevOps and CSIRT workflows. These results also highlight its ability to substantially reduce the manual effort traditionally required to consolidate historical PDF reports into actionable vulnerability intelligence.

Future work will focus on improving extraction accuracy through schema-aware validation and consistency checks, expanding support to additional scanners and heterogeneous report formats, incorporating local privacy-preserving models for sensitive operational environments, integrating the pipeline with vulnerability management platforms for continuous monitoring, and evolving the extracted data into knowledge graph representations to support correlation, prioritization, and threat intelligence enrichment.

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